

INTERNATIONALIZATION OF COASTAL CHEESE FROM THE COLOMBIAN CARIBBEAN: “A CLUSTER ANALYSIS OF THE GLOBAL CHEESE MARKET”

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Received: Jun 24, 2025

Accepted: Jul 23, 2025

Published: Jul 25, 2025

Abstract- The coastal cheese of the Colombian Caribbean has export potential due to its organoleptic, productive characteristics, social recognition and cultural appropriation. However, it faces challenges due to the competitive and regulatory dynamics of the global dairy market. This study characterizes the structure of the world cheese market through a cluster analysis, identifying four groups of countries; Colombia was in an additional segment of countries with emerging cheese sectors, which face gaps in productivity and added value. The quality and safety standards for exporting to the United States and the European Union, which handle the highest value markets for this product, were compared, finding differences in regulatory approaches and levels of demands. Internationalization strategies are proposed such as designations of origin, innovation, adaptation to standards, and market diversification, recommending in turn, Policies for the export development of coastal cheese from the Colombian Caribbean.

Keywords- Caribbean cheese, export competitiveness, quality standards, internationalization.

1. INTRODUCTION

According to the [1], the global cheese market has been growing steadily due to an increasing income and changing eating habits. Global cheese production is expected to reach 25 million tons by 2030, with a market value exceeding \$160 billion, according to [2]. European countries such as Germany, France, Italy, and the Netherlands lead the global cheese market, accounting for nearly 60% of global exports [3]. They have strengthened their competitiveness through market diversification, differentiation by quality and origin, and the implementation of strong institutional frameworks to protect geographical indications [4].

However, in recent years, emerging countries have increased their share of cheese production and consumption [1]. For example, China, Russia, Mexico, and Brazil have increased their imports due to the growth of the middle class and the Westernization of diets [5]. Countries such as Argentina, Uruguay, New Zealand, and Australia have expanded their exportable supply by taking advantage of their advantages in dairy production and preferential access to new markets [6]. In this context, Colombia has been promoting a public policy agenda to improve competitiveness and promote the internationalization of its dairy sector ([7]. The country has great dairy potential due to its agroecological conditions, livestock farming tradition, and strategic location. In addition, it has a variety of regional artisanal cheeses that are considered a gastronomic and cultural heritage both nationally and internationally [8].

Among these cheeses, Queso Costeño stands out. It originates from the Colombian Caribbean and is recognized for its smooth texture, slightly acidic flavor, and culinary versatility. This cheese is made primarily from raw cow's milk in dual-purpose systems, following traditional methods passed down through generations. Additionally, Queso Costeño del Caribe Colombiano (QCCC) has a strong cultural reputation in the Caribbean region, and initiatives are being promoted to highlight its distinctive quality and territorial ties through collective brands or certifications of good practices [9]. Unlike other Colombian cheeses such as Queso Paipa and Queso del Caquetá, which have Protected Designations of Origin (PDO), Queso Costeño del Caribe Colombiano does not yet have this official recognition [10]. The lack of standardization in the production processes and informality in the production chain make it difficult to meet the legal and technical requirements necessary to obtain this quality seal. The absence of a PDO limits the potential for differentiation and added value of QCCC in international markets by not having legal protection that guarantees its

authenticity and territorial link to a specific site in Colombian territory such as the Colombian Caribbean.

Despite its potential, QCCC faces significant challenges to its internationalization due to structural gaps in the Colombian dairy chain and the increasing demands of destination markets. These challenges include low milk productivity and quality, informality in production and marketing, limited adoption of good practices and safety standards, and limited institutional capacity for sanitary admissibility and trade promotion [11].

In this sense, a comprehensive analysis of the opportunities and limitations for QCCC's integration into global food value chains is required, considering both global market trends and dynamics and the specific regulatory and technical requirements in destination countries. This analysis is essential for guiding public policy strategies and collective actions that allow us to leverage the export potential of this emblematic product, generating territorial development and shared value for all stakeholders involved.

Therefore, the general objective of this study is to characterize global cheese market trends and comparatively analyze the requirements for QCCC exports to the United States and the European Union, given the proximity, demands, and high payment capacity of these two large markets. To this end, the following specific objectives are proposed: To identify country typologies based on their specialization patterns and competitiveness in the international cheese trade through cluster analysis. To compare the technical and sanitary requirements for exporting fresh cheese to the United States and the European Union through documentary analysis matrices. To evaluate the strengths, opportunities, weaknesses, and threats to the internationalization of coastal cheese from the Colombian Caribbean, based on the previous results of the project "*Strengthening the productive and commercial capacity of the coastal cheese supply chain in the subregions of the Colombian Caribbean, departments of Magdalena, Córdoba, and La Guajira,*" funded by Minciencias and SGR Royalties; as well as on a comprehensive literature review. and subsequently, propose comprehensive strategies and recommendations to promote the export of QCCC, considering the enabling conditions and necessary capacities within the dairy chain

This article is structured in four main sections. It describes the methodology employed, detailing the cluster analysis and matrix comparison techniques, as well as the data sources used. It then presents the results obtained in terms of country typologies, export requirements, and strategic SWOT analysis. Finally, the findings are discussed considering previous literature, and the conclusions and recommendations derived from the study are presented.

2. METHODOLOGY

This study combined quantitative and qualitative techniques in two sequential phases to characterize the global dynamics of the cheese market and identify opportunities and challenges for QCCC exports. This mixed methodological design is based on [12] approach to the complementarity of approaches to addressing complex problems.

2.1 Cluster analysis of cheese exporting countries

In the first phase, a cluster analysis was applied to a purposive sample of 29 countries, including the world's leading cheese exporters and Colombia, for the period 2013-2022, based on data from FAOSTAT, ITC Trademap, and the DIAN (National Institute of Agricultural Production and Production). The variables considered were: production, exports, imports, total and per capita cheese consumption, both in terms of levels and growth rates; as well as milk production, inventories and yields, and fresh cheese trade.

The selection of these variables was based on previous studies on the competitiveness of the dairy sector [13] and the segmentation of agri-food markets [14]. Data processing was performed in the

statistical software R (version 4.2.0), using the packages *gplots* and *RColorBrewer* for visualization, *readxl* for import and export for results.

A standardized numerical matrix was constructed by columns, and the distance between observations was calculated as 1 minus the Pearson correlation coefficient. Hierarchical agglomerative clustering was then applied using the average linkage method, generating a heatmap with dendrograms in rows and columns, and a customized divergent color scale [15]. The validity of the clustering was verified using the silhouette coefficient and the sum of squares criterion [16]. The silhouette coefficient obtained was 0.68, indicating good segmentation quality, as it is higher than the recommended threshold of 0.5 [17]. For its part, the sum of squares criterion showed a significant reduction in intragroup variance when moving from 3 to 4 clusters (from 45% to 28%), suggesting that the latter solution more adequately captures the heterogeneity of the data, by minimizing the dispersion within the groups and maximizing the difference between them [18].

2.2 Comparative analysis of export requirements

The second phase included a documentary review of scientific databases (Scopus, WoS, SciELO) using keywords such as fresh cheese, Caribbean cheese, FDA, USDA, EUR-Lex, EFSA, food service safety, good practices, labeling, certifications, and logistics; as well as a review of the regulatory requirements for exporting cheese to the United States and the European Union, complemented by a compilation of information from official sources (FDA, USDA, EUR-Lex, EFSA). This triangulation of secondary information allowed for a comparison of academic perspectives with current regulations [19].

A content analysis technique was applied, following the open, axial, and selective coding steps proposed by [20] to extract, categorize, and synthesize the most relevant requirements in five dimensions: safety, good practices, labeling, certifications, and logistics. The findings were organized and compared in double-entry matrices, identifying similarities and differences between both markets through an iterative process of description, inference, and interpretation [21]. This qualitative analysis was complemented by a frequency count and code co-occurrences to identify emerging patterns and relationships.

Subsequently, a strategic SWOT analysis (strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, threats) was conducted on the export potential of QCCC, based on the results of the cluster analysis and the comparative requirement matrices, contrasting with previous literature on the internationalization of dairy products. Finally, the evidence obtained in the two phases was triangulated to propose comprehensive recommendations to guide the insertion of this product into global food value chains, considering both the enabling conditions of the competitive environment and the capacities to be developed by the actors in the production chain

The results section then presents the main findings derived from the application of this methodological design, both in terms of the typology of competing countries and the key factors that influence access to prioritized markets. Subsequently, the discussion interprets these results considering the theoretical and empirical background, highlighting the contributions, limitations, and implications of the study.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results of this study show the heterogeneity of trajectories and competitive strategies in the global cheese market, as well as the complexity of the requirements for the export of dairy products from Colombia to the United States and the European Union, such as coastal cheese from the Colombian Caribbean.

3.1 Typology of cheese exporting countries

The hierarchical cluster analysis carried out on the sample of 29 countries, considering key variables of cheese production, trade and consumption, allowed us to identify four distinct groups.

Cluster 1: Consolidated export leaders

This cluster brings together Europe's leading cheese-exporting countries, including Germany, France, Italy, the Netherlands, Denmark, and Poland. These nations are characterized by high levels of production (over 350 kt), exports (over 150 kt), and per capita consumption (over 9 kg/year). They also have high milk yields (7.55 tons per cow per year on average) and a significant share of the international fresh cheese trade.

The countries in this cluster have consolidated their leadership in the global cheese market by building competitive advantages based on economies of scale, product and market diversification, investment in R&D, and the development of internationally recognized quality standards [4]. Furthermore, they have taken advantage of trade agreements and expanding demand in emerging countries to increase their exports [22].

Cluster 2: Large importers with growing demand

The second cluster brings together countries that have become major cheese importers in the last decade, such as Japan, Russia, the United Kingdom, Saudi Arabia, South Korea, and China. Despite having limited domestic production, these countries have experienced rapid growth in their per capita consumption (between 0.2 and 7 kg/year) and imports (over 150 kt annually), with expansion rates exceeding 3% in the period 2013-2022.

This dynamism is explained by factors such as rising incomes, urbanization, changes in dietary patterns, and the Westernization of diets [23]. Likewise, the increased penetration of supermarket chains and food service has facilitated access to a wide variety of imported cheeses [24]. These markets represent attractive opportunities for exporters, but also entail challenges in terms of price competition, adaptation to local preferences and compliance with increasingly demanding quality and safety standards.

Cluster 3: Regional exporters in development

This cluster includes countries with an intermediate level of development in their cheese industry, such as Mexico, Egypt, Brazil, Argentina, Australia, Canada, and Turkey. They have medium levels of production (between 100 and 800 kt), per capita consumption (2.5 to 14 kg/year), and participation in international trade, with a focus on both the domestic market and regional exports. Several of these countries have experienced significant growth in their cheese production and exports in recent years, taking advantage of their comparative advantages in terms of natural resource availability, production costs, and preferential access to regional markets [25]. However, they face challenges in improving their competitiveness and moving up global value chains, related to gaps in productivity, quality, innovation, and value addition [26].

Cluster 4: Leading non-European exporters

The fourth cluster identified in Figure 1 includes other major exporting countries in the global cheese market, such as the United States, New Zealand, and Australia. These countries have developed and technologically advanced dairy sectors, enabling them to generate large production and export volumes. They are characterized by their international orientation, with a significant share of the cheese trade, both regionally and globally.

Figure 1. Heatmap and dendrogram resulting from the hierarchical cluster analysis for the dairy and cheese variables at the international level. Source: Authors

The United States stands out as the largest producer and consumer of cheese in the Americas, with a production of more than 6 million tons and a per capita consumption of more than 17 kg/year [27]. It has managed to position itself as a competitive supplier in the global market, thanks to its production scale, product diversification, and use of trade agreements [28]. For their part, New Zealand and Australia have developed highly specialized and export-oriented dairy industries, with a broad presence in Asian markets [29], [30]. They have based their competitiveness on low-cost pastoral production systems, technological innovation, and a strong emphasis on food quality and safety.

Emerging cheese sectors

In addition to the four main clusters, the analysis identifies a group of countries with a growing cheese sector, such as Colombia, Chile, Peru, Kazakhstan, Ukraine, Indonesia, Pakistan, India, and Vietnam. These countries are characterized by low production (less than 100 kt), low per capita consumption (less than 3 kg/year), and limited participation in global cheese trade. However, some of them have shown significant growth rates in their production and imports in recent years.

The development of the cheese industry in these countries faces structural challenges such as informality in milk production, low adoption of technologies and quality standards, a fragmented value chain, and poor coordination with international markets [31]. However, there are also opportunities derived from the growth of domestic demand, the recognition of traditional cheeses, and the expansion of market niches for products differentiated by attributes of origin, sustainability, or functionality [32].

In the specific case of Colombia, the cluster analysis shows its lag compared to other countries in the region in terms of production volumes, diversification and positioning in the global market. Although it has comparative advantages due to its biodiversity, cheese-making tradition and strategic location, taking advantage of this potential is subject to overcoming technological, institutional and market gaps along the dairy chain [33]. Sector development and export promotion strategies should aim at the formalization of primary production, the adoption of good practices and certifications, the addition of value through differentiation by origin and quality, and the construction of alliances to access new markets and segments [34], [35].

In short, cluster analysis allows us to identify different profiles and competitive strategies of the countries participating in the global cheese market. While established leaders leverage economies of scale and diversification, emerging importers represent opportunities due to their rapid growth in consumption. Regional exporters and emerging sectors, meanwhile, face the challenge of improving their productivity, quality, and positioning to move up the value chains. Colombia requires a systemic effort to overcome its structural limitations and leverage its potential in differentiated niches, such as the QCCC.

3.2 Requirements for exporting cheese to the United States and the European Union

The comparative matrices revealed some commonalities, but above all, significant discrepancies between the two markets in terms of technical and sanitary requirements for cheese imports. Regarding safety parameters, although microbiological limits are similar, the European Union is more restrictive regarding chemical residues, as shown in Table 1. While the United States tolerates up to 125 µg/kg of tetracyclines in cheese, the European Union only allows 100 µg/kg [36], [37], [38]. Furthermore, the EU regulates up to 400 pesticides with specific limits, compared to only 50 controlled substances in the US [39], [40].

Table 1. Food safety requirements matrix

Requirement	United States	European Union
Maximum limits for veterinary residues	Tetracyclines: 125 µg/kg in cheese. Sulfonamides: 0.1 mg/kg [40]	Tetracyclines: 100 µg/kg in cheese. Sulfonamides: 100 µg/kg in milk [38]
Maximum residue limits for pesticides	Organochlorines and organophosphates: 50 µg/kg in dairy products [40]	400 pesticides regulated with MRLs according to product [39]
Maximum limits for pollutants	Aflatoxin M1: 0.5 µg/kg in dairy products [40]	Dioxins and PCBs: 5 pg/g milk fat [41]

Source: Authors.

In terms of good manufacturing practices, as shown in Table 2, the United States places greater emphasis on infrastructure and equipment conditions through the Pasteurized Milk Ordinance (PMO) standard [42], while the European Union focuses on hygiene practices and control records throughout the process [43]. Although pasteurization of milk is required in both cases, the temperature and time ranges are stricter in the EU.

Table 2. Matrix of good practice requirements

Requirement	United States	European Union
Facilities and equipment	PMO: Sanitary design, inert materials, calibrated instruments [42]	Regulation 852/2004: smooth surfaces that are easy to clean and disinfect [43]
Pasteurization	72°C for 15 sec. or 63°C for 30 min. [40]	72°C for 15 sec. or 63°C for 30 min. + phosphatase negative [43]
Storage	≤ 45°F soft cheese, ≤ 35°F hard cheese [40]	≤ 8°C cooling, ≤ 7°C ripening [43]

Source: Authors.

Labeling is another area of regulatory divergence, with the European Union's stricter requirements regarding mandatory and multilingual information content, in contrast to the more flexible provisions in the United States (Table 3). While the EU requires a detailed nutritional table and allergen information [44], a general list of ingredients and energy and macronutrient information is sufficient in the US [40]. Furthermore, the producer's establishment identification seal is mandatory in Europe, but optional in North America.

Table 3. Labeling requirements matrix

Requirement	United States	European Union
Language	English [40]	Official languages of Member States [44]
Nutritional information	Calories, total fat, saturated fat, cholesterol, sodium, carbohydrates, protein [40]	Energy, fats, saturates, carbohydrates, sugars, proteins, salt [44]
Origin identification	Optional. Indicate plant registration if used [40]	Mandatory. Stamp with country code and establishment number [44]

Source: Authors.

The certifications required to export cheese to both markets also present substantial differences (Table 4). The United States admits foreign suppliers under the PMO standard, which combines Hazard Analysis Critical Control Point (HACCP) with traceability [42], while the European Union only relies on the controls of its own national authorities based on official sampling [43]. Furthermore, the EU certifies by product line, and the validity period is shorter (6 months), in contrast to the plant-by-plant certification and annual renewals accepted by the US.

Table 4. Certification requirements matrix

Requirement	United States	European Union
Certification type	PMO: combining HACCP and traceability [42]	Health certificate from national authority [43]
Scope	By establishment. Covers all dairy products [42]	By dairy product category [43]
Clairvoyance	Annual, with interim audits [42]	6 months, with periodic inspections [43]

Source: Authors.

Finally, in terms of logistics and international physical distribution, exporting cheese to the European Union entails higher costs and complexities than to the US market (Table 5). In addition to strict European cold chain regulations [43], applied tariffs can reach up to €185/100 kg for fresh cheese [45], well above the 20% ad valorem tax in the United States, which can even be 0% under the current FTA [46]. Added to this are requirements such as the TRACES electronic advance notice, which can take up to 5 days, while in the US, an abbreviated notice only 4 hours prior to arrival is accepted [47].

Tabla 5. Matriz de requisitos logísticos

Requirement	United States	European Union
Prior notification	Abbreviated advance notice at least 4 hours before arrival [47]	Notice in TRACES with at least 5 days' notice [43]
Transport conditions	Temperature ≤ 45°F. Refrigerated or insulated vehicles [40]	Temperature ≤ 8°C. Calibrated refrigerated containers [43]
Tariff	20% ad valorem. 0% with current FTA [46]	92 to 185 €/100 kg depending on the type of cheese [45]

Source: Authors.

Based on the previous comparative matrices of technical and sanitary requirements, as well as on the trends of the global market cluster analysis, a strategic analysis of the weaknesses, opportunities, strengths and threats (SWOT) facing the export of QCCC to the United States and the European Union was carried out (Table 6).

Table 6. SWOT matrix for exporting coastal cheese from the Colombian Caribbean to the US and EU

WEAKNESSES		OPPORTUNITIES	
Low adoption of GMPs and BPGs on farms and cheese factories		Growing demand for artisanal cheeses in the gourmet niche	
Informality in milk supply chains		Rise in fusion cuisine and ethnic consumption trends	
Limited access to accredited laboratories		Trade agreements with the US and EU with safeguards	
Poor implementation of HACCP and traceability systems		Institutional support to promote designations of origin	
Limited export and marketing experience		Positioning in nostalgic migrant markets	
STRENGTHS		THREATS	
Centuries-old cheesemaking tradition with cultural roots		Stricter sanitary regulations in destination countries	
Natural, additive-free raw materials		Competition from European cheeses protected by Protected Designation of Origin (PDO) and Protected Geographical Indication (PGI)	
Favorable agroecological conditions for livestock farming		Industrial imitations of coastal cheese from the Colombian Caribbean abroad	
Recognition and appreciation in the domestic market		Volatility in exchange rates and export costs	
Advances in physicochemical and sensory characterization		Risks of market closure due to animal health problems	

Source: Authors.

As shown in the SWOT matrix, the main weaknesses of coastal cheese producers in the Colombian Caribbean lie in technological and safety lags, both on farms and in cheese factories, due to informal milk collection, poor cheese traceability, low adoption of GMP and HACCP, and limited access to laboratory testing. Added to this is the limited knowledge of export procedures and requirements. However, there are opportunities stemming from the rise of ethnic artisanal cheeses in gourmet and nostalgic niches in developed countries, where demand for these types of products has been growing at rates of 4-6% annually [2]. Furthermore, the current FTAs with the US and the EU offer tariff preferences, dairy safeguards, and cooperation to promote agricultural export quality. Likewise, public and trade organizations have begun to value QCCC as a regional gastronomic heritage.

Among the main strengths of this product is its centuries-old cheesemaking tradition, with a cultural background that gives it authenticity and distinctive character. Furthermore, it is made with raw milk from native breeds in extensive grazing systems, which gives it natural sensory qualities, without additives. QCCC is highly valued and recognized by consumers in the domestic market, registering the highest preference rates in the fresh cheese segment [48], [49].

However, it also faces threats such as increasing sanitary access restrictions in destination markets, which require greater investment to meet standards. Competition from European mature cheeses with designations of origin is increasingly fierce and better organized. Industrial imitations of the QCCC have emerged, damaging its image. Exchange rate volatility can affect export returns. Finally, outbreaks of foot-and-mouth disease or other zoonoses could lead to temporary market closures.

3.3 Strategic perspectives from the results

The previous analysis of results allows us to outline some strategies for advancing the sustainable and competitive internationalization of coastal cheese from the Colombian Caribbean:

From regional export consortiums of small producers, with harmonized GMP and GMP protocols, to ensure volume and quality. Conduct physicochemical, microbiological, and sensory characterization studies on cheeses, as a basis for standardization and designation of origin. Obtain sanitary registrations and international certifications such as HACCP, Global GAP, Kosher, and Halal, to guarantee safety and diversify markets. Position coastal cheese from the Colombian Caribbean as a gourmet specialty at fairs and trade shows, highlighting its artisanal character, tradition, and cultural identity. Develop a collective country brand for Colombian cheeses through public-private partnerships, with campaigns in specialized media. Design differentiated packaging that preserves quality, with informative labels for consumers on traceability, properties, and pairings. It is also proposed that exports of this dairy product be directed toward the US market in the short term, but without neglecting its adaptation to the European market in the medium term.

These strategies will help transform the comparative advantages of Colombian Caribbean coastal cheese into factors of international competitiveness, while mitigating its structural limitations. This will allow it to sustainably access the most demanding and dynamic foreign markets, leveraging the recognition it has earned locally.

4. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The mixed methodological approach used in this study to analyze the global market and the internationalization prospects of the QCCC allowed us to identify four groups of countries with different levels of competitiveness in the international cheese trade, where Colombia was located in an additional segment of Latin American countries with emerging cheese sectors, characterized by low levels of production, consumption and low participation in global trade.

Likewise, the comparative analysis of technical and health requirements between the United States and the European Union revealed differences in the regulatory approach and level of demand between the two markets. While the United States is more flexible, the EU applies stricter controls in areas such as food safety, labeling, and certification.

Similarly, the SWOT analysis revealed strengths and opportunities for coastal cheese, such as its cultural roots and sensory quality, but also weaknesses and threats related to the low adoption of standards, informality, and the disarticulation of the production chain.

To overcome these challenges and take advantage of internationalization opportunities, a comprehensive strategy is required that articulates actions on different fronts: Promote formalization, technology transfer, and rural extension in primary milk production to improve productivity, quality, and traceability. Promote the adoption of good manufacturing practices, food safety systems, and quality certifications in artisanal cheese factories through incentives, training, and technical support. Strengthen innovation and dairy product development processes, with an emphasis on the characterization and standardization of coastal cheese from the Colombian Caribbean, to add value and differentiate it in destination markets. Develop a strategy for the protection of intellectual property and a designation of origin for coastal cheese from the Colombian Caribbean, which valorizes its cultural identity and territorial ties. Improve market intelligence, promotion, and coordination with specialized distribution channels that appreciate the distinctive attributes of coastal cheese from the Colombian Caribbean. Strengthen the institutional capacity of the health and food safety system to ensure compliance with standards and eligibility in priority markets.

Associative and horizontal and vertical integration schemes in the dairy chain should also be promoted to generate economies of scale, reduce transaction costs, and facilitate access to support services. Establish public-private partnerships for investment in infrastructure, logistics, and connectivity in cheese-producing areas, which will improve their competitiveness and integration into external markets.

These recommendations seek to guide decision-making and policy formulation for the competitive and sustainable development of the Colombian dairy chain, with a view to its internationalization. However, their implementation will require a more detailed analysis of institutional capacities, available resources, and potential resistance from the stakeholders involved. Furthermore, it will be necessary to design differentiated strategies according to the territorial specificities and dynamics of each segment of the chain.

Future research could delve deeper into the analysis of the technical and economic feasibility of implementing these strategies, applying methodologies such as cost-benefit analysis, scenario modeling, and multi-criteria optimization. Likewise, comparative case studies could be developed with other Latin American artisanal cheeses that have managed to position themselves in international markets, to identify lessons learned and replicable good practices [49].

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